

CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF THE MARMARAK MEDICINAL PLANT (SALVIA OFFICINALIS) AND USE IN PEOPLE'S MEDICINE

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Annotation: In this article, there are comments on the geographical distribution, botanical description, chemical composition and use in folk medicine of the Dorivor mavrak plant found in Uzbekistan.

Key words: medicinal Salvia, essential oils, inflammation, infertility, fragrance, enuresis, stimulants, phytoestrogens.

Аннотация: В данной статье даны комментарии к географическому распространению, ботаническому описанию, химическому составу и использованию в народной медицине растения шалфей лекарственный, обнаруженного в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: шалфей лекарственный, эфирные масла, воспаление, бесплодие, ароматизаторы, энурез, стимуляторы, фитоэстрогены.

Medicinal herb - *Salvia officinalis* – Sage lekarstvennyy

Botanical description: The medicinal plant belongs to the Lamiaceae family.

Perennial semi-shrub growing 20-50 cm tall. The stem is numerous, branched, multi-leafed, four-sided, the lower part is slightly woody. The leaves are simple, long-banded, the ones in the upper part of the stem are unbanded, and they are opposite on the stem. The flowers are short-stalked, small, and form spike-like circular inflorescences at the top of the stems and branches. The flower is curved, the calyx is two-lipped, sertuk, the corolla is two-lipped, blue-purple, the male node is two, the female node is four-lobed, located at the top. The fruit consists of 4 nuts. blooms in June-July.

It is grown in the Mediterranean countries in Moldova, Ukraine, Krasnodar, Crimea and Uzbekistan.

Salvia officinalis

Mavrak leaves are harvested by hand three times a year, starting from flowering. In the first and second harvest, only the leaves at the bottom of the stem are removed. In the third harvest, in September, all the leaves on the stem and the upper part of the stem - the tip are collected and dried in attics or air dryers.

Chemical composition. All parts of the plant contain essential oil. The leaves contain 0.5-2.5% ellr oil, alkaloids, flavoring substances, flavonoids, ursolic and oleanolic acids and other compounds.

Essential oils in medicinal marmarak consist of a mixture of organic substances, including all saturated and unsaturated compounds, aliphatic, cyclic and aromatic hydrocarbons, terpenes, alcohols, fatty acids, phenols, complex ethers, aldehydes, ketones, lactones and includes nitrogen and other organic substances containing sulfur. Oxygen-containing compounds and their esters give essential oils their fragrance. Sesquiterpenes are the high-boiling fraction of essential oils. The chemical composition of the essential oil varies depending on the age of the plant, the climate of the place of cultivation and the period of growth.

Use in medicine. Preparations of medicinal leaves are used as expectorants, disinfectants, and anti-inflammatory drugs for upper respiratory tract infections, mouth (stomatitis and gingivitis) and throat gargles. This herb is an antiseptic and anti-inflammatory agent, and due to the abundance of essential oil and camphor in its composition, it is used in the treatment of diseases of the respiratory tract and gums. The famous physician Hippocrates called marmarak a sacred plant.

V1, PP, C drugs in the composition have an effective effect on the nervous system and metabolism, strengthening the walls of blood vessels. Marmarak plant is consumed as tea in Turkey. Turks call this tea "adachayi". The leaves of the plant are used to add flavor to various salads and fish dishes. The essential oil contained in marmarak is used in pharmaceutical practice to improve the smell and taste of liquid medicinal forms. In Bulgaria, marmarak plant products are used for gastritis, colitis, flatulence, liver and gall bladder diseases, and in Germany, marmarak products are used to treat the central nervous system. for sedation and night sweats, in Poland for nocturnal enuresis and hair loss, in Austria for stomach and intestinal diseases, for the treatment of laryngeal mucosa, in the USA to add it to soups and salads, and the Chinese to drink it as a tea as he rose.

In modern medicine, the products of the mavrak plant are widely used in infertility and childlessness. Mavrak's help in conceiving women is related to the phytoestrogens in the chemical composition of mavrak. So it helps in estrogen hormone deficiency in women. Even in climactic situations, estrogen hormones decrease in women, and in such cases, if women are treated with a mavrak plant, the balance of hormones will be normalized, and climactic situations will be alleviated by rejuvenating the female organism. Mavrak also treats various inflammatory diseases in the male organism, improves the quality of sperm and ensures the movement of spermatozoa towards the female ovaries. From the information given above, it can be concluded that the medicinal plant Mavrak is used in medicine for various inflammatory diseases, infertility, psoriasis, stomach and liver diseases, angina, nocturnal enuresis, and the main composition is essential oil. can also be used as a flavoring agent.

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